

**A DISCUSSION OF A CONFUSING GROUP OF SPECIES IN THE
GENUS *CONUS* (GASTROPODA-CONIDAE), WITH THE DESCRIPTION
OF A NEW SPECIES**

by
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INTRODUCTION

For several years, I have devoted special attention to gathering a large number of study specimens within a particular group of cones, which have been unceremoniously lumped as *Conus magus* Linnaeus, 1758. By systematically collecting specimens in various growth stages, recording population occurrences and observing locality differences, I could test and reach conclusions which enable me to single out a species which I now describe hereunder and propose as a new taxon which I dedicate to Professor Bernard M. Tursch.

Conus turschi sp. nov.
(Pl. 1, figs. 1-2; Pl. 2, fig. 4)

Description: Shell smooth and subcylindrical, with a conic spire and acute apex, consisting of 11 whorls, the first 4 post-embryonic, being beaded. The surface of its declivous whorls are imperceptibly convex and narrowly folded towards appressed sutures, causing the spiral profile to appear slightly stepped. Striation of spiral whorls are strongly incised with the first two adapical volutions more deeply grooved, creating twin ridges of greater prominence to give an appearance as if each whorl is girdled with a distinct ring. Shoulder is angulate but lightly carinate without a pronounced keel. The elongate body whorl has sides which are very slightly convex down the whole of its attenuated length. The anterior end is sculptured with about 8 raised sulci and the columella is strongly plicated; its outer lip, sharply trenchant. The ground color is fulvous and the pattern is quite variable, but always within a theme of vermicular chocolate brown streaks, to specimens which are completely without these maculations. Some specimens have these ornamentations only at the upper portion; still others, only very sparsely streaked or none at all. The holotype was selected for its more profuse markings. The spire is decorated with dark brown speckles in a radial pattern; the body whorl, encircled with dark brown streaks in perpendicular rows. A median spotless belt separates two broader transverse bands of a darker tawny sha-

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de, with another clear zone at the lower section. Aperture has a nacreous-white interior. The periostracum is light brown and translucent, becoming opaque with maturity.

Holotype (Figs. 1 and 2): 82.5mm × 35mm deposited in the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva together with Paratype No. 6 measuring 76mm × 30mm (immaculate pattern).

Paratypes: No. 1 measuring 72mm × 28.5mm and No. 7 measuring 73mm × 31mm (immaculate pattern) deposited in American Museum of Natural History, New York.

No. 2 measuring 69mm × 28.5mm and No. 8 measuring 77mm × 31mm (immaculate pattern) deposited in the Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Brussels.

For subsequent distribution to other museums:

No. 3 : 63.5mm × 26.5mm

No. 4 : 51 mm × 22.5mm

No. 5 : 61 mm × 25 mm

No. 9 : 80 mm × 33 mm

No. 10 : 78 mm × 33 mm

No. 11 : 81 mm × 31 mm

No. 12 : 74 mm × 33 mm (immaculate)

Type locality: Trawled in depths of 20 to 40 fathoms in the Andaman Sea off Kantang, S. W. Thailand.

Distribution: Philippines, Indonesia and the South West Pacific region, down to the coast of Queensland. Populations of congeneric species may be identified from Indian Ocean areas after further study.

Discussion: Because so many species have been erroneously considered as either conspecific, or just forms, of *C. magus*, it becomes necessary to first identify this particular species so that comparisons which will be made can be properly recognized and understood. KOHN (1963) selected a specimen as neotype of *C. magus* (Journal Linn. Soc. Zool., Vol. LXIV, Pl. II, f. 21) and

remarked that its characteristic features are given by REEVE (1843: pl. 33, sp. 100) and KIENER (1845: p. 283). From these two sources, *C. magus* was described as a shell cylindrically turbinated, rather elongated, white, ornamented with large scattered, livid olive, orange-stained spots and encircled with interrupted, dotted or white-articulated olive-brown lines; spire convex, apex raised, tinged with rose. Both authors also included an extensive but questionable list of what had been assumed to be varieties of *magus*.

It is, of course, recognized that *C. magus* is a common species proliferating throughout the Indo-Pacific region, and although variegated with different coloration, it is nevertheless not the polytypic species which its voluminous, and utterly ridiculous, synonymy would suggest. No attempt has so far been made to sort out how or why so many of these shells, have been lumped as one. Many are not even look-alikes. However, they are sympatric in most cases, which could be a possible explanation for the confusion.

The need to segregate these *magus* varieties is not necessarily relevant to the present discussions because the new species does not possess any features which could be mistaken for any of its presumed varietal forms. *C. magus* is a small to medium sized shell and some of the species which could be identified either as congeneric, if not conspecific, are: *C. epistomium* Reeve, 1843, *C. assimilis* A. Adams, 1853, *C. consul* Boivin, 1864, *C. signifer* Crosse, 1865, *C. tasmaniae* Sowerby, 1866, *C. borneensis* Sowerby, 1866 non A. Adams, 1848. However, the new species cannot be included in this same complex, as it must be placed in a different generic grouping, which includes: *C. raphanus* Hwass in Bruguière, 1792, *C. daullei* Crosse, 1858, *C. consors* Sowerby, 1833, *C. anceps* A. Adams, 1853 and *C. poehlianus* Sowerby, 1887. Compared with *magus*, each of these species is invariably much larger or wider in size, with a conic spire and very little individual color variation, to provide any apparent affinity.

The new species is closest to *Conus poehlianus* Sowerby, 1887 (Fig. 3) in its morphologic composition. Both shells are conic and subcylindrical. They attain lengths of over 80mm, but when young, are similarly patterned with two transverse bands of darker tawny color with interspatial zones of a lighter shade. However, differences immediately emerge when only mature specimens are compared. The spiral whorls of *Conus poehlianus* have a more convex surface, and although incised with spiral threads, the sutures are only closely-coiled and do not have the two raised ridges to create the illusion of being girdled with spiral rings. Also, its shoulder tends to be somewhat wider and more rounded and the sides taper flatly down its length. It additionally becomes whiter with maturity, and is never decorated with any maculations, in any case. I suspect *C. poehlianus* could possibly be endemic to New Britain Island. The morphological and distributional differen-

ces of other congeners compared with the new species are:

C. raphanus is a medium to large subcylindrical shell, having a low spire with wider and prominently bulging shoulders. Its ground color is similarly banded and decorated with transverse rows of brown interrupted dotted lines; sometimes, with brown flammules also displayed, depending on its locality (Hwass figured two other varieties in Tableau Pl. 341, f. 1 and f. 8). It ranges from the Philippines to South West Pacific and some islands in Central Pacific. It does not occur in the Andaman Sea.

C. daullei (Fig. 8) is a medium-sized shell with a centre white band separating two brown zones with distinctly marked rows of dark brown dotted lines. It cannot be confused with *raphanus* because the shoulders are never bulging but well-rounded with flat sides. It is not seen in the Andaman Sea and ranges from Mindanao to Queensland.

C. circae (Fig. 9), another medium-sized shell with a white band below the shoulder level and another at the mid-section of the body whorl. It is brown-colored and decorated with flammules, and often overlaid so extensively with large blotches as to give some specimens a melanistic appearance. The shoulders are carinate and the flat sides tend to constrict more rapidly at the basal end. It is sympatric with *daullei* and not found in Andaman Sea.

C. consors: no type is available for examination. However, Sowerby described the species as «broadheaded, yellow, with orange bands, a little contracted at the centre». The figure illustrated (Thes. Conch. Vol. III, Pl. 20, f. 492) shows a center band separating two brown zones without maculations. Specimens are sometimes decorated with brown flammules, depending on its origin (Fig. 7). It can be distinguished from *anceps* by its more depressed spire and broader body whorl. It is often confused with *C. raphanus* when the latter is not distinctly patterned. Its range is extensive: from the Andaman Sea to the Philippines down to South West and Central Pacific.

C. anceps: (Fig. 5) the morphological features of this species are distinctly monotypic; it never varies. It is colored with bands almost identical to such specimens of the new species which are immaculate (Fig. 4). The structure of its spire is also very similar. The distinguishing characteristics setting the two apart are its bulging shoulders developed on maturity, straight sides and a more contorted columella. Observe the broader body whorl of the shell next to it (Fig. 6) which is shaped almost the same as *consors* except that it is more ovately oblong. That shell is a specimen of *C. floccatus** without its usual maculations, and serves to demonstrate co-

gently the dangers of misidentification when based on just the coloration of a shell. *C. anceps* is sympatric with the new species in the Andaman Sea and the Philippines, but not yet seen in other Pacific areas.

RESUMO

O autor descreve uma nova espécie, a partir do estudo de exemplares que têm sido erroneamente identificados como *Conus magus* L. Ao mesmo tempo, traça um panorama global dos taxa associados, ao *C. magus* e bem assim ao novo taxon, o qual é comparado e separado de cada uma das espécies mais próximas.

A espécie agora proposta é originária das Filipinas, Indonésia e do Sudoeste do Pacífico e é designada em honra do Prof. Bernard W. Tursch, conhecido malacologista belga.

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